

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BLEBOO****FIRST NAME: ANTHONY****PROGRAM CODE: DGEP****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE****INSTRUCTOR: PROF GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author did not use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium provided by EUCLID

The author used the MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

1. Topic selection (EUCLID 2021, 8)
2. Approach and style ((EUCLID 2021, 41)
3. Punctuations (EUCLID 2021, 15)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34)
5. American English (EUCLID 2021, 5)

APPROACH AND STYLE FOR SUCCESSFUL ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

“An academic essay is nonfictional writing produced as part of Academic Work” (EUCLID 2021, 7). The application of this statement varies in various academic spheres and levels depending on the protocols in particular institutions and the country's education policy. Jacqueline and Patrick said, “Like many forms of specialist writing, essay writing is a set of conventions that you need to follow when completing your coursework” (Jacqueline and Patrick 2011, 9). In other words, essay writing is required to acquire the relevant certificate of program completion in a manner prescribed by the awarding institution.

My response paper will look at the approach and style of writing a successful academic essay with an insight into key concepts such as topic selection, punctuation, Plagiarism, and referencing. Finally, I will provide insight into American English, its identities, and its differences from other English varieties.

2) APPROACH AND STYLE

a) Topic selection

Cleenewerck and Gulma state that “academic essays seek to provide an answer(s) to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence” (EUCLID 2021, 7). This statement may be interpreted as developing or providing a solution to an identified challenge or providing direction for problem-solving. Therefore, utmost care or extra effort is required in establishing what topic to research and what it seeks to achieve or what issue it is expected to address, failure of which can lead to a disastrous essay not providing the intended results.

Fred and Beverly state that “some of the most successful thesis and dissertations simply extend the knowledge base one step further in an area by examining a new variable within a well-established line of inquiry, collecting data on a different sample, testing a new methodology, or introducing a new statistical technique” (Fred and Beverly 2008, 2). In other words, most academic essays are continuations, expansions, or variants of existing work. A successful essay begins with a good topic, and it is advisable, in doing so, to establish a broad view and progressively provide a focus for the direction or objective of the essay to ensure that expected outcomes are realized. Researchers have usually been challenged with meeting timelines for completing their thesis and its objectives due to the inability to initially establish a focused direction for their ideas. Most of these researchers have to change their topics to provide a focus.

b) Approach and Style

Cleenewerck and Gulma state, “It is best to start as early as possible. One of the initial things required for writing is to have enough time to read, research the topic, think, and write. It is never advisable to procrastinate” (EUCLID 2021, 7). They further advise that after understanding the chosen topic, one needs to research it and subsequently organize ideas by developing a writing plan. There is a well-known saying, “one who fails to plan is planning to fail.” Academic essay writing can only be successful with good planning. Planning should be time-bound for successful academic essay writing.

It will be unfortunate if I fail to state that it took me a couple of weeks to appreciate the idea of Key Concepts. Key Concepts are used in developing a Response paper as part of the EUCLID doctoral coursework, which is alien to me compared to my previous academic work. However, I must thank my supervisor for rejecting my initial draft, which I wrote from my understanding of the critical concepts.

Over the years, individuals or research groups have developed various approaches to academic essay writing. MunLing states four critical approaches to essay writing. These include: (1) the Straight-into-it approach, (2) the Jigsaw Approach, (3) the wait-and-see approach, and the (4) the building approach (MunLing 2010, 132). A cursory review of each informs you that the building approach, which adopts a logical, systematic step-by-

step approach, could be the best as the writer has a more organized, in-depth, and thought-through approach to ensuring the final product meets the expectations.

Cleenewerck and Gulma advise using a style guide (EUCLID 2021, 40). They state, “A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent” (EUCLID 2021, 40). Consistency is vital in writing essays for specific objectives, and academic essays are no exception.

3) PUNCTUATIONS

Understanding punctuation and its relevance in successfully writing an academic essay are most appropriate. The Cambridge dictionary describes punctuation as “the use of special symbols that you add to writing to separate phrases and sentences to show that something is either a question or other.” This is better interpreted as a means of bringing better appreciation to a sentence by introducing symbols at various positions. A successful academic essay cannot be achieved without introducing punctuation where relevant. Comprehension is paramount in essay writing, and punctuation helps achieve this. These include apostrophes, brackets, bullet points, colons and semi-colons, commas, dashes and hyphens, ellipses, full stops, exclamation, and question marks, amongst others.

John indicates two uses for the apostrophe, either for contraction or possession. He, however, is against its use for contraction in a university essay but encourages its use for possession (John Biggam 2020, 18). This is understandable, considering university essays, like all other academic essays, are formal and should be accorded the importance they deserve. Similar arguments for the use or otherwise of the other punctuations can be made for a successful academic essay.

4) PLAGIARISM

Cleenewerck and Gulma describe Plagiarism as “when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2021, 34). The Holy Bible in Mark 12: 17 says, “Well, then,” Jesus said, “give to Caesar what belongs to Caesar, and give to God what belongs to God.” This is a literal analogy for addressing Plagiarism. The use of other person's works without giving credit where its due is known to have resulted in litigation and even prosecution. This is of common occurrence in the music industry, and academia is no exception. In academia, however, it is an issue of ethics and the need to recognize another person's work. It is considered unethical if this is not done. Cleenewerck and Gulma suggest that Plagiarism can be avoided if you “properly cite the author or source that has provided the information you are using” (EUCLID 2021, 34). Citing can be used in various forms, such as officially inviting someone to court or referencing a person in a suit. In essay writing, it is described as the method used to indicate where information is sourced. Cleenewerck and Gulma write that can be done in the form of in-text citations as quotations or paraphrasing (EUCLID 2021, 34). References are a solution to the problem of Plagiarism and come in various

forms. Cleenewerck and Gulma write, “Only references guard against plagiarism which is a serious academic offense” (EUCLID 2021, 34).

5) THE AMERICAN ENGLISH – IDENTITIES AND DIFFERENCES

Zoltan writes that “it is interesting if we consider the fact that American English, and in many ways, American mentality (or mindset or world view) have evolved into an enormously influential pattern that is recognized, appreciated (often also criticized) and imitated worldwide” (Zoltan 2000, 10). The influence of America has permeated most of the fiber of life worldwide, and even the English language is not spared.

It is common knowledge that over the recent past, the English language has penetrated and spread throughout other languages, and American society is no exception. America is known as a land initially owned by indigenous native Indians, and it is therefore interesting to research how the English language and, for that matter, American English became the dominant and ultimately the official language of these North American communities.

a) Identities of American English

American English cannot be described without giving attention to identities or properties that distinguish it from the other English varieties. This is because, in practice, there are notable differences in the spelling of keywords and the tone of a Brit from that of an American. Zoltan identifies some critical properties of American English, which he classified as “economical, regular, direct, democratic, tolerant, informal, prudish, inflated, inventive, imaginative, success, and action-oriented” (Zoltan 2000, 13). Economic power, democracy, and successes in technological invention are measurable characteristics of the United States of America, and it is not surprising to have them defined as some critical properties of American English.

Ingrid states that three varieties of the English language have emerged, which can be categorized into structural, perceptual, and discursive (Ingrid 2002, 9). He indicates that, even though American English went through the various stages as any other English variety, the only possible difference, namely comprehensibility, played perhaps a more critical role in the rudimentary leveling of the first stage because the traditional dialects spoken by the settlers were more different from one another than those in colonies which were settled late. This indicates that there were stages in the development of American English for which the diversity of the settler languages influenced the first stage.

b) Differences in American and British English

As indicated in the previous paragraph, American English is better described as a variety of English languages rather than seen as a different language from British English.

Notwithstanding, researchers have established some notable differences between the two languages, which is the basis for my further research in this paper. Paul state, "by using tools such as WordSmith to identify spelling differences, keywords such as *color/colour*, *labor/labour*, *behavior/behaviour amongst others*, were revealed as different in spelling to the similarly pronounced keywords in British English" (Paul 2017, 2).

Pronunciation is another identity of American English that makes it different from the other English varieties. Christopher states that Noah Webster, a well-known American lexicographer, in his best-selling American Speller, published in 1783, suggested that giving every syllable its due proportion in sound may be responsible for the pronunciation differences between American English and British English. Christopher also indicates that Noah Webster further writes that "other differences result from the fact that all languages change over time, and since the separation of the two varieties, American English has not changed in the same way as British English" (Christopher 2007, 2). This statement is quite controversial, considering America is instead a land of various migrants compared to Britain, which has remained the home of Brits.

6) CONCLUSION

Successful writing of an academic essay requires adherence to the various established norms of the certificate award institutions and the styles and, most importantly, citing the relevant information source.

American English has developed into one of the most preferred English language varieties due to the dominance of the United States of America. Spelling and pronunciation, however, are identities that have differentiated America English from other English language varieties. It is expected to influence any varieties that the world would grow to develop and will eventually drive world geopolitics. These reasons will influence the preference for American English over British English.

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